

Experimental Article

Tales of Evaluation in School Mathematics

Melissa Andrade-Molina¹

Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso

ABSTRACT: This is the tale of the power effects of evaluation in the shaping of the desired child. It maps, by using historical and cultural strategies, the circulating truths about standardized assessments and the need of learning mathematics at school. The analysis takes discourses around large-scale assessment and curricular guidelines to portray that the role granted to assessment for the normalization of mathematics education is intertwined with neoliberalism. Within these circulating discourses, assessment systems were taken as the path to achieve quality as a guiding system to help in decision-making processes. This paper is aimed at problematizing the need of higher proficiency in mathematics as a fixation of raising scores to achieve the illusion of producing the desired scientific self.

KEYWORDS: *rhetorical experiment; sociopolitics of mathematics education; ideology critique*

Once Upon a Time...

...in 1958, in a country named Chile there began to increase the necessity of a scientific and rational self for the economic development of the nation. Suddenly the goal and structures of education were rapidly modified to reach a ‘new desired citizen’. The aim was to escape from the literary humanism and focusing instead on science and technology (Avalos, 1970; Nuñez Estrada, 1973; Vidal, 2010). And so, the journey began, a path from the spotlight of older days to the dreams of a brighter future. Voices were raised and decisions were made. In 1964, a big organization called UNESCO collaborated with the Inter-Union Commission on Science Teaching to sponsor the gathering of renowned scholars with the task of eloquently argue about science teaching and economic development of the nations across the land. These wise scholars launched the movement of “modern mathematics” that was widely discussed because of its implications to science. Oh, those wishes to possess the key to grasp even with one finger that vast and rich knowledge. Mathematics was thought as an effective tool significantly beneficial for the improvement of science teaching (Deschamps et al., 1970). And, of course, schools were aimed at teaching a mathematical language useful for the sciences (Misrachi & Aspée, 1967). Clear as water the answer

¹ Melissa Andrade-Molina is a professor at Pontificia Universidad Católica de Valparaíso. Melissa is concerned about how school mathematics has been used to exert violence against children in the name of progress. Email: melissa.andrade@pucv.cl. <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1535-3194>

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emerged, a curriculum in which the teaching and learning of mathematics required as its basis the development of logical thinking (Michelow, 1969)... All for those beloved sciences! *Ash nazg durbatulúk, ash nazg gimbatul, ash nazg thrakatulúk, agb burzum-ishi krimpatul*²... a key, a tool, a ring to control them all.

But... that was only the beginning. “Who would possess that precious ring?” they argued. Should it be someone able to speak the dark tongue?³ And so, quickly school mathematics was thought as a form of language. Mathematics was taken as a tool that enabled students to logically, graphically, and symbolically express their ideas—or the ‘objects of the mind’: *objetos de pensamiento* as they called it (de Graf et al., 1979b). As brush strokes, carefully placing the paint, stroking logically, displacing the best techniques to produce a masterpiece of the mind, the need of the dark tongue spread across all nations. Suddenly it became an official and universal language for them all. Here and there, people talked about how ideas can be voiced in other languages, being materialized by all mother tongues. But something moving through the wind started to sound. A whisper, an echo, was rapidly displaying across every country in their Kingdom, a sound voicing ‘human capital’. Human capital, what was that? The Council of the Wise⁴ told the story behind that whispered, encrypted vision. Human capital was taken as the “knowledge skills, and attributes embodied in individuals that facilitate the creation of personal, social and economic well-being” (OECD, 2001, p. 18). Knights in shining armour, all together working for the same cause. *For all. For progress.*

Not all of them were privileged enough to possess the ‘precious’;⁵ not all of them were able to speak or understand the dark tongue... They were knights without a sword! Ring bearers without a ring, but trying desperately to reach their dreams with the promises of a brighter future. So, they trained—and they *were trained*, and they *were assessed* to become knights. At the blink of an eye, national assessment arrived to appraise abilities on mother and dark tongue. The unveiling of a tool able to rate the main elements considered for the fabrication of a competent and rational knight. Mother and dark tongue were taken as the key to achieve economic progress; on the one side, to test current changes, on the other, as a means to set standards (Bravo, 2011): mother tongue not only to learn how to eloquently enounce thoughts, neither to enjoy a pleasant story... but also, mother tongue to understand and comprehend mathematical instructions, an operational and technical mother tongue useful for the sciences (Ministerio de Educación & Centro de Perfeccionamiento Experimentación e Investigación Pedagógica [Ministerio de Educación & CPEIP], 1967). As a consequence, Nazgûl⁶ emerged in the form of standardized assessment systems, testing skills and abilities... chasing the One Ring, haunting the ring bearers, fighting knights.

In the beginning, Nazgûl were chosen as keepers of the rings of power with the aim to improve by helping them to make proper decisions. But the rings were used to obtain status, wealth, and to control everything, every move. As time progressed, Nazgûl were drawn and seduced by the

² Inscription upon the One Ring that symbolises the power possessed by the Ring to control all other rings: *One Ring to rule them all. One ring to find them. One ring to bring them all. And in the darkness bind them.* Excerpted from J. R. R. Tolkien’s (1968) *The Lord of the Rings*.

³ Also known as the *Black Speech*, the dark tongue of Mordor is the language Sauron created as the unifying and official language of Mordor. The inscription upon the One Ring is in Black Speech written in Elvish letters.

⁴ The *Council of the Wise*—also known as the *White Council*—is a group of the wise wizards and elves of Middle Earth. Held in the Second Age to discuss on the power of Sauron, and in the Third Age with the purpose of uniting and directing the forces of the West, in resistance to the growing power in the Hill of Dark Sorcery—*Dol Guldur*.

⁵ The One Ring.

⁶ Sauron gave nine rings of power to nine Kings of Men. Those kings used the rings to achieve prestige, wealth, and a great power. But they became corrupted by the power of Sauron. The rings left the Nine as wraiths, Ringwraiths, Black Riders... Nazgûl.

promises of welfare, they were eclipsed by the power of the rings, they became corrupted, they became wraiths, they lost their original purpose... (Andrade-Molina, 2017a, 2017b). There was a time in which standardized assessment was thought as a mean of measuring abilities, as an objective and quantitative scientific method for decision-making. There was a time in which standardized assessment would provide useful and important information for policy makers. There was a time in which Nazgûl were kings... Kingdoms in need of an army... Oh, those dreams of increasing knights in shining armour, of scientific and rational knights for the economic development of the nation. All in the name of progress!

As time passed, Nazgûl evolved and transformed, always haunting, always seeking for the precious. They changed to be in complete harmony with shifting eras. The trends regarding the teaching and learning of mathematics are in a constant *vinyasa*,⁷ always moving, always flowing, as water streaming through the river. Psychology was one of the flows, pouring its wisdom into school mathematics research: “[I]deas are not isolated in the psyche, these are to form mental structures,” they used to say (de Graf et al., 1979a; Ripamontiz & Prieto, 1992). Changes were made in order to fit the new standards. As a progression, school mathematics was taught according to the levels of psychological development, although it is impossible for new water not to mix, very nicely and gracefully, with the old river. Songs were written and sung throughout the whole Kingdom.

To modern psychology ideas are
arranged as mental structures,
these cannot exist isolated in the psyche.
As the notion of “triangle”
should be linked to other concepts:
line, segment, angle, polygon, vertex...
Whoever learning these notions
should be equipped with previous ideas
and their symbols. Oral and written!
Hooray!⁸

Mental structures aimed to be increased, as an enlargement of the mind, as an expansion of connections to collect wisdom: the sign of intellect. School mathematics, the dark tongue, was still thought as a form of developing the desired logical thinking the Kingdom thought that knights needed, and this “need” was used to promote, within people, a desired to learn useful mathematics to overcome daily life challenges in a motivated and entertained fashion (Ripamontiz & Prieto, 1992): “logic is the basis of mathematics,” they said (Walker, 1978a, p. 11). Oh, those promises of learning enough dark tongue to control the power of the One to obtain wealth and welfare! In the little country named Chile, people realized they were very far away from the Kingdom’s desires. So close, yet so far away to be considered in the fight for Middle Earth, still invisible, still unevolved, still underdeveloped, still... too little. Logic was once taught by the use of tautologies and demonstrations, but everything evolves (see Figure 1). “God created the Universe and the order that governs it. Man needs logic to understand it,” they said (Díaz & Guidici, 1970, p. 1).

⁷ *Vinyasa* is a Sanskrit term often use in Yoga. It has been taken to define a “sequential movement that interlinks postures to form a continuous flow” (Maehle, 2007).

⁸ Fragmented adaptation of de Graf and colleagues (1979b, pp. 5–6): “From the point of view of modern psychology ideas are arranged as mental structures, this means that new ideas cannot exist isolated in the psyche. As the concept of a triangle should be linked to other concepts of plane, line, segment, angle, vertex, triangular region, polygon, etc. The human being who is learning this geometrical notion should be equipped with a “grounding” of previous ideas and their corresponding system of oral and written symbols.”

Oh, that language of the universe carefully placed to reveal the mysteries of creation! “[Dark tongue entailing] the study of logic, [dark tongue needed] for making possible to reason correctly and rigorously in the search for truth” (Díaz & Guidici, 1970, p. 1), for truth: enigmatic veracity. “Remember that the new philosophy of mathematics teaching requires telling the truth, nothing but the truth, but not necessarily the whole truth” (Michelow, 1969, as cited in Walker, 1978b, p. 5).

X	Y	X	∨	Y
V	V	V	V	V
V	F	V	V	V
F	V	V	V	V
F	F	F	F	F

Figure 1. Logic taught by using tautologies (Díaz & Guidici, 1970, p. 5).

And suddenly, logic through tautologies was not enough. The pursuing of logical thinking prompted by problem solving started: a quest. A quest for them to conquer success through reason! And, without hesitation, Nazgûl commenced testing ring bearers for them to be logical and rational, for them to battle for their ambitions and aspirations, enchanting them to succumb to the power of the One. Studies were made trying to understand which skills Nazgûl considered valuable to be assessed (National Research Council [NRC], 2001). International surveys—TIMSS—, national standardized tests—SIMCE—, even classroom evaluations—*evaluación de aula*—, seeking all places where Nazgûl become visible:

Habilidades	Evaluación de aula	SIMCE 8° 2004	TIMSS 2003
Manejar Conocimientos y Procedimientos.	67%	10%	15%
Usar Conceptos	7%	17%	20%
Resolver problemas de rutina	19%	55%	40%
Razonar	6%	17%	25%

Figure 2. Skills Nazgûl assessed.⁹

They realized that, in this little country, they were far behind because they were chased by diverse standards. They were able to see how the skills (*habilidades*) considered valuable for some were not the same in all situations: classroom (*evaluación de aula*), national (SIMCE) and international (TIMSS) surveys. Oh, those Nazgûl targeting different types of abilities, Nazgûl with different styles of fighting, Nazgûl hunting and seeking! One black rider steering 67% at procedures and knowledge performance (*manejar conocimientos y procedimientos*), the solving of problems was not worthy enough. One black rider more interested in testing skills for problem solving (*resolver problemas de rutina*), 55%, and for the using of concepts (*usar conceptos*) and of

⁹ Table that shows the comparison between the percentages of skills measured by three types of assessment. The table is taken from Meckes (2007, p. 364).

reasoning (*razonar*). The last black rider focused on problem solving and reasoning abilities instead. Black riders, ringwraiths... Ringwraiths haunting, ringwraiths chasing, but in diverse ways... mutating! However, black riders become more effective when unified, when bind into one: Nazgûl. And so, the Ministry of Education of this country developed a program in which classroom assessment aimed at bearing a resemblance to national and international standardized surveys. Oh, those desires of uniformity to be average and more, to be at the top, to possess the precious, to possess success! Nazgûl testing skills in dark tongue to overcome the challenges they pose, not to be fluent in the Dark Speech, but in being able to use the power of the Ring to outface Nazgûl.

There was a time in which Nazgûl were kings of men. There was a time in which they used its sovereignty to measure some abilities of men to become knights. Memories of younger fantasies to assess “fundamental knowledge in mathematics, skills, numeric judgment and concepts usage” (Ministerio de Educación & CPEIP, 1967, p. 21)! But the past is so far in time, distant and blurry shadows in the dark...

As the rings commenced to exercise their influence, the assessing of knowledge performance in mathematics began to transform. Suddenly, it was not enough to learn the structure of the dark tongue. It was not enough to learn the basic mathematical knowledge needed to understand scientific advances and technology (Valdivia, 1975), the basic dark tongue to better understand the world and to control the power of the One. In 1975, teachers should lead students to discover the structure of mathematical knowledge, by themselves, because mathematics was believed to be qualitative (Ministerio de Educación Pública, 1975). So, the logical structure of the Black Speech ought to be pragmatically developed by young minds, as a blossoming intuition of mathematically axiomatized logic.

So many knights trying to reclaim their shining armour, so many knights training and agreeing to be trained in the hopes of a brighter future.¹⁰ Measures were taken, decisions were made, standards were released, and knights were assessed. Learning standards that evaluated “what [they] should know and can do to display, in national tests, appropriate levels of achievement according to learning objectives set in the current curriculum” (MINEDUC, 2013, p. 4). Assessed knights, assessed ring bearers, in the need to know how qualified they are to continue their journeys, to carry the ring, to fight for Middle Earth!

Oh, mathematics! “Abstract science *par excellence*, [you are] not only an instrument, but a knowledge structure and a form of thinking through which [you, treasured mathematics,] contributes to culture” (Ministerio de Educación, 1980, p.2). Oh, mathematics! Without you knights will be so intellectually uninvolved.¹¹ School mathematics, childish game, solving puzzles, connecting dots, answering riddles, making structures, discovering... Teaching to “analyze problems, to formulate questions, to organize information to obtain new evidence [...] to solve problems” (MINEDUC, 1996, p. 101). Seeing not just answers but also evaluating performance, evolved knights, well trained, logical, and reasonable, evolved knights (Bamón et al., 2001). Oh mathematics! Black speech that “contributes to the development of communication abilities [since you, cherished mathematics, help] to analyse and interpret charts, graphs and formulas, [...] to register, to describe, to explain ideas, arguments, relations and procedures” (Bamón et al., 2001, p. 8).

¹⁰ Mathematics is the “study of the principles of logic applied to a state of abstraction barely inferior to the one of the exact sciences [in which] school mathematics is intuitively supported and almost all students’ ideas are susceptible to be graphically represented. [Students] should learn a language code to acquire the specific ideas” (de Graf et al., 1979a, p.5).

¹¹ Mathematics is acknowledged for contributing to students’ training—*formación del educando*—and their intellectual development (Ministerio de Educación, 1980).

Gradually, challenges started to be trickier, questions started to mutate, to transform... Firstly by using tools to help them overcome each encounter they faced. Swords in the hand of knights! They were equipped and instructed with the basic techniques, the basic movements to face battles, to defend themselves. They were challenged and they challenge themselves. Before standardized tests emerged, before kings of men become Nazgûl, classroom assessment was concerned only with results, only with answers. So, they let knights to use weapons, to memorize formulas, there was only one solution, only one procedure, only one aim. Knights were armed with protractors to measure angles, and they learned how to use their armaments to solve queries, to unravel riddles, to develop practical skills (see Figure 3).

Measure the following angles by using a protractor and write each value in the corresponding letter.

—They asked in 1962.

Figure 3. Measure of angles by using a protractor (de Graf & Marin, 1962, p. 14).

School textbooks were designed with the aspiration of promoting in these brave beings an active participation in the teaching and learning of mathematics (de Graf & Marin, 1962), in instructing and practicing the dark tongue. And so, queries became more abstract, less tangible. They were unarmed: Knights at the mercy of reason and logic! Equipped only with the power of their minds, knights embarked in epic fights. New techniques were displayed. There were no protractors nearby to be used. They had to calculate angles by using theorems and their own rationalities, subtracting. The images accompanying the tasks were now only a mere depiction to better understand the battled field, they did not have to be accurate anymore. These were solely representations of shadowy abstractions. Suddenly, and without hesitation, kings were seduced by the measuring of abilities; they felt they were able to scientifically track progress to predict future mastering of the Black Speech (Ministerio de Educación & CPEIP, 1967): Oh, attractive quantifications! Standardized assessment emerged as poltergeists able to follow knights' steps, able to track national performances, able to nationally assess abilities, to measure quality, to measure progress, to measure all.

What is the measurement of beta if alpha is 60°30'?

—They asked in 1967.

¿Cuánto mide el ángulo beta, si el ángulo alfa mide 60°30'?

- A) 19° 30'
- B) 121° 30'
- C) 120° 30'
- D) 119° 30'

Figure 4. Supplementary angles' tasks (Ministerio de Educación & CPEIP, 1967, p. 8).

As time passed, aspirants to knights and ring bearers became more comfortable with these new techniques of fight. They became used to utilize only the power of their minds. As Jedi mind tricks, solely using the force. For kings, this was not enough. Something was missing even though knights left their swords aside. Riddles continue their journey, moving, shifting. Kings judged with their monitoring eyes (Campos-Martínez, Corbalán & Inzunza, 2015). The questions they asked to 14-year-old aspirants to knights in 1967 became less intriguing, less challenging. Kings, in the attempt of improving their armies, wondered: how were knights taking decisions? How were ring bearers analysing situations? In classrooms, teachers instructed young Padawans towards the virtues of solving problems, of managing strategies, of taking their own decisions instead of waiting patiently for instructions. Of course, there was still one option to be taken as correct, one possibility to achieve the best possible results to win the disputes, but now... Now many paths were available, so many possible ways of mastering and using the Dark tongue, as three branches, opening, splitting towards sunlight.

The following is a theorem by Lewis Carroll's (Alice in Wonderland's author) that was published for the first time in London in 1899. Carefully analyse its demonstration and find the mistake.

[Theorem: Sometimes an obtuse angle could be equal to a right angle]

—They asked in 1996.

5. A continuación se presenta un teorema enunciado por el profesor Lewis Carrolls (autor de *Alicia en el País de las Maravillas*) que fue publicado por primera vez en Londres en 1899. Analice cuidadosamente la demostración y encuentre el error.

Teorema:
A veces un ángulo obtuso puede ser igual a un ángulo recto.

- Sea ABCD un cuadrado. Se toma el punto medio E de AB. y. por E. se traza EF, perpendicularmente a AB. que cortará al lado DC en F. Se tiene: $DF=FC$.

Figure 5. Task that required the use of problem-solving strategies (Ministerio de Educación, 1996, p. 107).

Oh, that desired of displaying a multiplicity of options for knights to learn how to make proper decisions to conquer success. Some tasks, not all of them, were about making demonstrations or carefully analysing the old strategies to find mistakes, probably to improve, probably for them not to make the same errors, probably for some other unexplained and mysterious reason. And although the tactics to approach the riddles changed, standardized assessment remained with the same structure, with the same format, options to take, decisions to make. But its focus was budged, problem solving was all they saw. 14-year-old aspirants to knights were asked to play with the knowledge they acquired, to develop strategies... as detectives solving mysteries, as Bard the

Bowman,¹² posing mathematically logical and reasonable tactics to kill Smaug,¹³ measuring the exact path of the Black Arrow to penetrate Smaug’s armour. Or as Gandalf the Grey opening the Doors of Durin “*Ennyn Durin Aran Moria. Pedo mellon a Minno. Im Narvi bain echant. Celebrimbor o Eregion tethant. I thiv hin*”¹⁴... “Mellon”.¹⁵

Observe the following figure formed by three equilateral triangles.
 What is the measurement of the marked angle?
 —They asked in 2005.

Observa la siguiente figura que está formada por tres triángulos equiláteros.

¿Cuánto mide el ángulo marcado?

- A. 60°
- B. 90°
- C. 120°
- D. 180°

Figure 6. Calculation of angles by using properties of triangles (Ministerio de Educación, 2005, p. 11).

Aspirants to knights, ring bearers calculating exact measures by remembering the properties of equilateral triangles. Oh, trickier and trickier queries for them to solve. But kings began wondering if it was possible to predict the results of the battles. Students kept answering problems, knights solving riddles, ring bearers making decisions but... kings remained thinking about other forms of materializing the future, a reliable oracle. And so, the “learning standards” were released. Oh, dear canons for classifying knights to predict their future performance!

Observe the following image. If ABC is a right triangle in B, what is the measurement of x?
 —They asked in 2013.

6. Observa la siguiente imagen:

Si ΔABC es rectángulo en B, ¿cuánto mide el ángulo X?

- A. 35°
- B. 45°
- C. 55°
- D. 65°

► Los estudiantes que alcanzan el Nivel de Aprendizaje Adecuado deberían resolver esta pregunta, ya que se requiere establecer un procedimiento apropiado para resolverlo, reconocer ángulos suplementarios, y saber que la suma de los ángulos interiores de un triángulo es 180°.

Figure 7. Query on the learning standards (Ministerio de Educación de Chile, 2013, p. 22).

¹² Bard the Bowman, also known as the Drangonslayer, was the man destined to kill Smaug with the Black Arrow. Bard then became the founder and first king of the Kingdom of Dale.

¹³ Smaug the Golden, the Impenetrable, was a dragon of the Third Age. Smaug was a fire drake known as the King under the mountain.

¹⁴ Inscription on the archivolt of the Doors of Durin, the Westgate of Moria, only visible in starlight and moonlight. “*The Doors of Durin, Lord of Moria. Speak friend and enter. Narvi made them. Celebrimbor of Hollin drew these signs*”. The Fellowship of the Ring.

¹⁵ “Mellon” is the word for friend in Sindarin. This word was the answer of the riddle inscription on the Westgate of Moria, and password to opening the doors.

And all began to crumble. The performances of knights started being labeled as adequate, elemental, or insufficient according to the standards (Ministerio de Educación de Chile, 2013), according to the desired skills kings wanted to prompt in schooling. Riddles were not only to assess their expertise on the dark tongue, but also for evaluating and predict their future actions, a future not only regarding their encounters with Nazgûl, but beyond. Problems shifting, turning as a gear system, carefully arranged, carefully displayed. The options that ring bearers and aspirants to knights decided to take (a, b, c, or d), were the path to the oracle to prophesy their whole life. Calculating the measurement of x was not naïve anymore. They needed to learn new techniques; they needed to compete with themselves to not be left out of the battles, to be considered as productive knights. Riddles of the past, of 1967 (Figure 4), were now considered to be insufficient by the new learning standards (Ministerio de Educación, 2013).

If \overline{AB} is a straight line, what is the measurement of x ?
—They asked in 2013.

1. Si \overline{AB} es una línea recta. ¿Cuánto mide el ángulo X ?

- A. 23°
- B. 67°
- C. 113°
- D. 123°

► La mayoría de los estudiantes que quedan clasificados en el Nivel de Aprendizaje Insuficiente resuelven esta pregunta, lo cual implica tener conocimiento sobre la medida de un ángulo extendido.

Figure 7. Query on the learning standards (Ministerio de Educación, 2013, p. 39).

And young 14-year-old aspirants to knights are now asked to solve problems that were asked in 1978 to 18-year-olds (Walker, 1978b). Oh, provoking levels! Oh, desired to be above average to score higher internationally. Oh, attractive dreams of progress and economic development!

Standardized assessment system...

useful instrument, reliable system to guide decisions (Campos-Martínez, et al., 2015).

Standardized assessment system...

to monitor and inform (Meckes & Carrasco, 2010).

Standardized assessment system...

for attending necessities to achieve quality (Olivares, 1996).

Standardized assessment system...

for efficiency to increase achievement (Carnoy & de Moura Castro, 1996),

to allocate resources (Lockheed & Hanushek, 1988).

Nazgûl pursuing decisions for economic growth, decisions for being less

underdeveloped, decisions for welfare! (OECD, 2014).

There was a time Nazgûl were kings of men, but the rings of power Sauron gave them started to corrupt them even more. Men became dependent on the rings... The rings of power, resulting outcomes of the tests, dammed kings until they become Nazgûl, until they become wraiths... And so, the rings were all they perceived... Numbers were all they glimpsed. Quantified 'reliable'

readings of the Chilean educational system. Rings of power to determine what should be improved for achieving greater quality. Dark tongue, rings of power, and Nazgûl all together subjectifying knights by using techniques to regulate their habits and desires.¹⁶ Oh, neoliberal dreams!¹⁷ Charming governmentality effectuated through the interest of knights, of governed knights.¹⁸ Desired greatness, the need of using the rings of power to achieve greater quality. Kings were no longer men; Kings of men were always *mortal men doomed to die*. Oh, effects of power for the fabrication of the Lord of the Rings: self-regulated self-entrepreneurs. Kings adding test samples in each students' school textbook, in each guideline for teacher, in most materials dedicated to the teaching and learning of school mathematics produced by the Chilean Ministry of Education. Pages and pages consisting of problems mimicking the one of large-scale assessment. But knights are not forced to answer the problems displayed in their guides, teachers are not forced to ask students the tasks displayed on the teachers' guidelines, but... Oh, these technologies of government! In order to be successful probably they will choose to engage in those practices, solving the samples not so innocently placed carefully in each text... for progress.

Bilbo Baggins¹⁹ did not learn how to speak the dark tongue, but he was not intended to control the ring of power, he was neither a mathematician nor a scientist. He had a great and long life, thanks to the power that the ring gave him. He was just a hobbit from The Shire, but he learned to handle the ring to his own convenience and ambitions, he became corrupted by its power. Bilbo became a knight in shining armour. He knew he needed the ring to be successful, he could feel it in every nerve of his body. He became dependent of the One... *One ring to rule them all, one ring to find them, one ring to bring them all, and in the darkness bind them. In the Land of Mordor where the Shadows lie...*

The End

Article continues on the next page.

¹⁶ Governmentality, in terms of Foucault, is aimed to generate cultural and historical subjects by using techniques to regulate the habits and desires of subjects. It is aimed for “arranging things so that people, following only their own self-interest, will do as they ought” (Scott, 1995, p. 202).

¹⁷ Neoliberalism is understood through audit techniques, quality management, financial standardization, participative management and private property ideologies, managers aim to transform the employees in ‘self-entrepreneurs’, individuals that self-regulate, self-direct and are continuously in a process of redefining their competences” (Cotoi, 2011, p. 116).

¹⁸ According to Cotoi (2011), governmentality is effectuated through the interest and values things get, “people are governed by and through their own interests” (p. 113), and, therefore, a neoliberal governmentality governs “by giving the impression that it is not governing” (p. 114).

¹⁹ Bilbo Baggins was a hobbit from The Shire. He was the fifth bearer of the One Ring (without knowing it was the One Ring) and the first to give it up voluntarily after six decades with it.

Appendix: Guide for the Tales of Evaluation

The One Ring	Is the Ring of Power able to control all other rings <i>The belief of needing science for economic progress and welfare</i>
Dark Tongue	Language created by Sauron as the official of Mordor <i>Mathematics language needed for the sciences/School math</i>
Nazgûl/Black Riders	Nine kings of men damned by Sauron <i>Standardized assessment system in mathematics (SIMCE/PISA)</i>
The Rings of Power	Nineteen rings to control and corrupt every race <i>Quantification/Numbers/“Scientific Methods”</i>
Ring Bearer/Knights	<i>Students/Citizen</i>
Lord of the Rings	<i>Desired Scientific Self</i>

Afterword: Alice and the Hatter

This manuscript was quite a journey. I was a Ph.D. student when I first wrote this manuscript. It was 2016. At the time, I produced creative writings with the data I collected for my thesis. My thoughts were that Foucaultian and Deleuzian perspectives in Mathematics Education were not everyone’s cup of tea, not even considered to be within the field. I wanted my readership to be, in fact, math educators, math teachers, and student math teachers, so I was writing with them in mind. I did not feel the need to talk about Foucault and Deleuze’s toolboxes. I did not want to dedicate an entire section to saying things they would not be interested in. So, my take was to produce pieces of writing that were more like stories than a traditional academic paper. But, in following my decisions, I encountered several walls that made me step back from my initial intentions.

My Ph.D. was all about moving away from traditional academic research. I was collecting data from unexpected places; for example, I was interested in examining how Euclidean Geometry has inscribed a path for scientific thinking and has introduced particular rationalities about what doing science is, but I did not look for data in math education, neither in related fields, such as mathematics and physics. I historically traced Euclid’s *The Elements* in other fields, such as theology and literature, to problematize the fabrication of the desired scientific self. A paper I wrote on the topic was rejected by three journals before finally being published as a conference paper at the *Mathematics Education and Society* Conference (MES).

I was lucky enough to be part of the *Disorder of Mathematics Education* movement proposed by Hauke Straehler-Pohl, Nina Bohlmann, and Alexandre Pais (2017). There I found a space to expand the creativity of my writing when this journey led to a special issue in *The Mathematics Enthusiast* Journal, where I got the chance to publish a comic far away from traditional academic writing. I was even asked to remove some of the text I added because I was afraid the comic could be rejected, like footnotes overexplaining some ideas, quotes, and references.

All of this leads me to this manuscript. With this, I felt I had failed to fit it into what is considered “proper academic writing”. This manuscript has been read and commented on by Paola Valero, Thomas Popkewitz, Erika Bullock, Alex Montecino, Gustavo Bruno, and Aldo Parra. I have lost count of how many times this tale has been rejected. The nicer comment I got was, “please, look at the type of papers we publish and resubmit your contribution once you restructure

your manuscript”. However, I also got comments about this not being academic or being an abomination to the field. Most of the time, the manuscript was rejected before the peer-review process. But, on some rare occasions, the manuscript was destroyed by the rude comments of colleagues hidden behind their anonymity. So, I kept this writing for myself for almost two years until I met Alex Moore.

At MES, we discussed academic publishing and blind peer review issues. Alex heard my experiences with editors and reviewers; I read some of the comments I received for one of my papers (not this one). He asked me if I had something I could submit to the *Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education*. Without a doubt, I sent him this manuscript. His positive attitude toward the effort put into this piece of writing and the untraditional open review process made me feel part of academia again. I remember telling Alex, “I think this paper found its home”. This leads me to the title of this afterword: Alice and the Hatter.

Felling inadequate, odd, and unwelcome has played an enormous part in my academic journey. Most of the time, I feel like the Mad Hatter. Not making sense, having to over-explain my thoughts in footnotes for some editorial decisions to make academic sense is exhausting. I even decided to stop writing for a while. What was the point in fitting into the templates of academic writing if what I consider valuable knowledge for society is getting lost because it remains hidden inside academia? Then Alice came in the form of Ana Lúcia Braz Dias. She sat and drank tea with me, metaphorically speaking.

She read this manuscript and began building on my thoughts instead of critiquing it. The “nobody will make sense of this if they don’t know Tolkien’s novels” mutated into “the same happens in Brazil”. The review process was a dialogue to enhance the manuscript rather than an opportunity to dismantle someone’s work. Crucial parts of the paper are now more readable because of her comments and feedback. Our conversations, even though Word doc comments, helped enrich the paper. Alex advised us to communicate whenever needed, so we sent back and forward the manuscript until we were both happy with the result (the process lasted almost an entire year). And I think she was the one that made this article better. I owe so much to her: the time she dedicated, and her willingness to stand with me throughout the whole process. I am truly grateful.

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As a matter of the form of presentation and the theoretical perspective of this article, the Figures contained herein have been reprinted from their original sources.

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